

Particulars of Educational Management in the Context of Global Changes

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ABSTRACT: In order to achieve quality management, it is necessary to consider the particulars that characterize it. For this, it is important to understand how educational management is defined; the way it evolved over time; the functions it performs; the role of culture in educational management, as well as the elements to be taken into consideration in setting school curricula or study subjects.

KEYWORDS: management, education, change, organization, development

Given that the results of education are found in society, in civilized behavior, i.e. the good growth demonstrated in the middle of society, education requires its own management, specific to its field of activity. In terms of education, Ioan Jinga's educational management is defined as "a science and an art of preparing human resources, of forming personalities, according to the finality accepted by the individual and society". (Jinga and Istrate 1998, 409)

Educational management has to do with both the theoretical part and the practical part of organizing the educational activity, with all forms of management of this activity: planning, coordination, and regulation. These prerogatives of management are largely based on communication, which underlies the achievement of the other functions of management while being the premise of inter-human relations.

In comparison to general management, pedagogy of education differs, according to Elena Joița, through specific reporting: to the finality of education (others in content

and determination), to the human resources trained (themselves in formation-development), to the activities centered on information, communication and participation through specific educational strategies (methods, means, organizational forms), the behaviors of the actors involved (based on motivation, responsibility, cooperation, logic, affectivity) under decentralization conditions (Joita 2000, 25).

Educational management, therefore, has a complex character, both through the actions /methods/techniques that ensure the functioning of the educational system, as well as through the multi-participative character (managers, teachers, scholars, parents).

Among the important characteristics of the educational management, the applicative one is an essential one: to structure the educational issue (the process, the various factors) according to the particularities of a certain class/collectivity and to fulfill the functional needs: in good correlation with the needs of the individuals, with the requirements of the society. To design and coordinate an educational system that produces influences on pupils' personality, for the benefit of their aspirations and lives, and linked to the broader dimension of society, is a great goal and a not a simple job.

The scope of management is wide, which is why Sorin Cristea considers that the specification of the educational management concept encounters serious methodological difficulties that come from:

- ✦ The origin of the general concept, launched especially at the economic level, oriented towards the management of the organization's resources in achieving its objectives, then also at the level of sociology, politology, psychosociology;
- ✦ The cultural tradition of management is unsuitable to the European - Latin - leadership model, distinct from the American pragmatic model;
- ✦ Insufficient pedagogical practice in the field of management involves adaptations of the management in other fields, at least of some basic concepts: efficiency, organizational relations, science and art of management, valorization of the psychological elements of the behavior of educators and educators, adaptation at various application levels (teacher, class, director, etc.). (Cristea 1996)

In order to achieve quality management in the field of education, all these difficulties must be carefully analyzed and overcome, as is also emphasized in the specific literature.

The state of research in the field, as the variety, amplitude, complexity of the approach, shows that the management of education is solved only interdisciplinary, it pursues criteria of efficiency and effectiveness, of educational success, by the superior use of human resources, content, processes relationships, specific strategies (Joita 2000, 22).

In the paper *Management: Fundamental Elements*, the authors Ion Stăncioiu and Gheorghe Militaru (1998, 1.4) tackle the meaning and use of the term management as follows:

Management is an English term of French origin [...] The semantic correspondent of management in Romanian is “leadership”. Lately, the term “leadership” is increasingly replaced by “management” due not only to the predisposition of the specialists and the public for the completion of the language with neologisms, determined by the obvious tendency to open the states to the outside, but also because this term has gotten an international recognition.

Dr. Carter McNamara (n.d.) refers to more conceptual management than semantic, describing it as follows:

Traditionally, the term “management” refers to activities (and often to the group of people) involved in four general activities: planning, organization, management and resource management. We note that the four activities reappear throughout the organization and are as integral as possible. The guidelines in management include the emphasis that leadership is thus different from management, and that the nature of how the four activities are done needs to be changed to accommodate a “new paradigm in management.

With direct application to the education system, school management “represents the leadership of the system and of the educational process, at the level of the basic units, institutionalized in the network: kindergartens, primary schools, gymnasium schools, lyceum schools “ (Cristea 2003, 54) having” a triple significance: practical activity (process), decision center and scientific discipline” (Negreț 2009, 1). Managerial activity involves the activation of the three functions, namely the planning-organization of the education system, the methodological orientation of the educational process, the regulation-self-regulation of the system and of the educational process, by their coordination and their corresponding structures (Cristea 2003, 43).

Educational management, thus exceeds empirical leadership, where problems are solved by “seeing and doing”, based on common sense, intuition, imitation models, experience, psychosocial and cognitive traits (Joita 2000, 26). Florica Orțan (2004, 128) emphasized, on the other hand, that:

Educational sciences and, in particular, educational management are facing great challenges, such as finding ways and means to influence the behavior of adults and especially young people so that they can adapt to such complex rules of the school in the Western countries and the notion of the transformations through which the Romanian society will pass in the next period.

Faced with the many challenges that the future holds, education becomes an indispensable tool for achieving human ideals. Therefore, ensuring quality education at present must be a fundamental option for all those involved in the educational process. One can safely say that education has a fundamental role in the development of the individual and society. Education is one of the means available to help reduce poverty, ignorance and oppression.

In a context in which educational policies are deeply criticized and economic and political reasons no longer constitute a priority, a few things are needed, namely:

- Constantly adapting education to the needs of society.
- Adoption of an ethic that contributes to the improvement of the quality of the educational act.
- Appropriate assessment of all those involved in the educational process.
- Encourage the continuous improvement of the teaching staff.

The existence of a close relationship between the teacher and the learner is also essential for the educational process. This connection aims at developing personality, forming individual judgment and sense of responsibility for each individual, so as to enable those involved in the educational process to anticipate and adapt to the changes around.

In this respect, the educational act must not be confined to transmitting information or knowledge. Consideration should also be given to how information is presented so that the learner can connect the solutions found to other problems within a wider context. In other words, Educational Management should help to develop the conditions for the permanent education of every person (Rotaru 2013, 7-11). Education management can, therefore, be viewed as a way of controlling activities aimed at achieving the objectives of an educational institution.=

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